

SYSTEM DESIGN WITH QUALITY ENGINEERING

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Abstract

This paper discusses the use of the Quality Function Deployment concepts during the conceptual design of a kinesthetically controlled flight vehicle. Specifically, the techniques were employed to increase the inherent dynamic stability of the vehicle through proper placement of critical components. The resulting design was robust to operator size and skill level as well as on-board weapon system and external environment induced oscillations.

Introduction

As military dollars shrink, the importance of the development of quality products increases. Good quality designs must be insensitive to functional variations caused by the environment, manufacturing and operator usage. Quality engineering results in reliable products that meet the needs of the user, performs its mission without variation, increases combat capability and has low monetary losses. In order to achieve such results, new quality technology must be applied in the design and manufacture of today's weapon systems. The quality engineering concepts developed by Genichi Taguchi are the key to making the seemingly incompatible goals of achieving high reliability and maintainability for future weapon systems at reduced development, production, and operation costs (4:1).

Quality concepts can be categorically divided into on-line quality techniques and off-line quality techniques. The off-line techniques are concerned with the design of the product where as the on-line techniques are used exclusively during the manufacturing process. This paper will concentrate on the application of the methods associated with the off-line techniques.

This paper discusses how Taguchi's quality engineering process was used in the conceptual design of a unique flight vehicle. Specifically, the statistical design techniques of parameter design were used to analyze the independent variables that influence the inherent dynamic stability of the vehicle. The inherent stability of the vehicle was primarily driven by the placement of the major subsystem components. The fundamentals of engineering and statistical design were used to arrive at the optimal subsystem configuration of the

vehicle. The emphasis will be on discussion of the parameter design phase.

The goal of parameter design is to take an organized approach to design tradeoffs so that the overall system performance is maximized while keeping cost a minimum. Cost will be incurred whenever the desired performance is not achieved. A prerequisite for parameter design is the identification of all applicable parameters that effect the performance of the system. These parameters fall into two broad classes: design parameters and noise parameters.

Design Parameters

The design parameters are the fundamental vehicle components that the design group has absolute control of and whose nominal settings can be specified. In this case, the design parameters selected came from four major subsystem areas and are identified along with their range of variation are shown in Table 1.

Design Parameters	Design Range
Man's CG Z Axis	20 to 40 inches
Fuel CG Y Axis	-5 to 5 inches
Fuel CG Z Axis	10 to 30 inches
Engine Angle	0 to 45 degrees

Table 1: Design Parameters

Noise Parameters

Noise parameters are those parameters that the designer has no fixed control over. These parameters are usually external to the design and represent sources of variation that affect system performance. When examining the major subsystems, several parameters fit into this category. The noise parameters used and their anticipated ranges are shown in Table 2.

Noise Parameters	Noise Range
Man's Weight	5th to 95th percentile
Operator Index	10 to 15
Fuel Load	5 to 400 pounds

Table 2: Noise Parameters

Performance Characteristics

In order to analyze the effects of the various design and noise parameters on system performance, some measure of the resulting performance must be established. It is important that this performance measure capture the essential elements of the desired characteristics for which the system is being designed.

Traditional aircraft stability and control analysis characterizes the handling qualities of a vehicle with the damping ratio and natural frequency. But, due to the uniqueness of the vehicle, it was determined that those measures alone did not fully characterize the dynamic stability. As previously discussed, one of the traditional measures of system response is its ability to damp out a perturbing force. But, the damping ratio alone did not completely capture the system response to an impulse input. The amplitude and frequency of the vehicle's oscillations were also important in characterizing the vehicle response. Theoretically, there is a finite angle through which the vehicle can roll before becoming uncontrollable. This concern was captured by attempting to minimize the amplitudes of angular positions, velocities, and accelerations. Thus, the dynamic stability of the system was characterized by forming a stability vector of three measures: maximum amplitude, natural frequency, and damping ratio. A stability vector as shown in Eq (1) was formed in both the pitch and roll axes.

$$\underline{S} = \begin{pmatrix} A \\ \zeta \\ \omega \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where:

\underline{S} = the stability vector

A = the maximum amplitude

ζ = the damping ratio

ω = the natural frequency

Although the stability vector characterized the stability of the proposed system, a single performance measure was desired. The parameter developed by the design team normalized all of the components, and provided a uniform direction of improvement. The resulting response variable developed is shown in Eq (2).

$$Y = \zeta + \log(1/A) + \log(1/\omega_n) \quad (2)$$

The variable combined the multiple objectives of increasing the damping ratio, decreasing the amplitude, and minimizing the frequency into one variable. The larger the mean value of Y , the better the dynamic stability characteristics of the proposed configuration. However, it is also desirable to design a system such that the variability of the response is a minimum. These two facets are captured in the performance statistic:

$$Z = 10 \log(E[y]^2 / \text{Var}[y]) \quad (3)$$

Experimental Design

The next step was to develop the experimental layout of the individual matrices. The selection of the type of experimental design used in each matrix will have a significant effect on the usefulness of the results.

The experimental matrix chosen for analyzing system response to the design parameters was a central composite design. The design layout used for this analysis was constructed from a 2^4 full factorial design, augmented with axial points and a single center point. It should be noted that the central composite design span the same design space as the full factorial but does not require as many runs. Thus, in comparison to a full three level factorial design, a savings of runs was achieved. This is a substantial savings as the number of noise parameters increases.

The selection of the noise matrix design was simpler in that there was less concern over the biases involved in the experimental design. The major item of importance is that the full range of values for each noise factor be spanned. The noise matrix was constructed using a 3^{3-1} fractional factorial design. Although there is significant aliasing in this noise matrix, it was felt that the generalized effect of each of the noise variables on the stability of the proposed designs could be determined.

Having identified the design matrix and the noise matrix, the total experimental design was constructed, and involved 225 experimental runs.

Data Analysis

The first step in analysis of the experimental design results was to calculate the performance statistic (signal to noise ratio) for each of the 25 proposed configurations. It is important to note that each of the 25 designs is characterized by a stability vector which has three components: amplitude, frequency, and damping ratio. Therefore, a performance statistic was constructed for each component of the stability vector in addition to the overall performance characteristic y . This was done so that the sensitivity of the individual components of the stability vector to the noise parameters could be investigated.

The next step was to examine the effects of the design variables on the actual stability performance characteristic. The purpose was to determine if there are any factors, among those that did not significantly affect the response of the signal to noise ratio, that do have an effect on the mean response of the stability measure. If such a variable did exist, then it could be used to increase the mean response without affecting the signal to noise ratio. To investigate the existence of this variable, an ANOVA was performed on the experimental design using the stability performance characteristic (Y) as the dependent variable. It was found that the set of significant parameters for the raw data was identical to the set of significant parameters for the signal to noise ratio model. Thus, there are not any adjustment parameters that could be varied that do not affect the variance of the response of the system's stability parameter.

Response Surface Analysis

Having chosen a carefully designed experimental layout, it was now possible to relate the system response Y to the varying levels of the design parameters. The regression coefficients for the significant design parameters were calculated and the resulting regression equations represent an approximation of the vehicle's stability response under the experimental conditions.

Before performing analysis on the system using these equations, it must be cautioned that the results are only valid for the range of the independent variables selected. Keeping this in mind, one of the best ways of understanding how the stability of the vehicle is affected by particular parameter settings was through the use of a graphical representation of the response function.

Graphical representations of the effects of changes in parameter settings of the design variables were constructed using regression relations. The response surface generated from the four different design variables was a hyperplane. Thus, a series of plots were generated showing the effect of two variable parameters on system performance with the other two parameters fixed at their nominal values.

As an example, the plots for the system response in the roll axis, with the fuel CG position in the y' axis fixed (at what was later determined to be the optimal setting) are shown in Figures 1,2 and 3.

This series of figures shows the significant effects on the system response for the three remaining design variables. First, the quadratic effect of the engine angle on the system's response is easily identifiable by the curvature in the response as the engine angle is changed. Similarly, the changing effect of the man's CG position is evident as the CG position of the fuel in the z' axis changes. This change is shown by examining the changing response shape from Figure 1 to 2 to 3. It is important to note that as the fuel CG position was raised, the magnitude of the response variable increased. Thus, if the optimal roll settings established earlier are examined in the figures, one finds that the optimal design settings result in the response surface in Figure 3.

In particular, when the man's CG position is as high as possible, the fuel CG position is as high as possible, and the engine angle is approximately 22.5 degrees, one finds that the optimal response is achieved. Notice that the surface is fairly flat at this point. This indicates that the system is less susceptible to slight changes in the parameters when they are set at these positions. Thus, the design is robust to slight changes in the settings of the particular design variables. This is beneficial because that indicates that the particular design settings do not have to be extremely precise. The system will respond in the same manner for relatively small perturbations around the optimal design settings, for example, high variability in design parameters translates into low variability in the response.

Optimal Design Settings

The final selection of the overall optimum design was made by examining the signal to noise ratio of the stability characteristic Y . A non-dominated solution set was established based on the above criteria for both the pitch and roll axes. The non-dominated solution set for the pitch axis was composed of two designs, while the roll axis contained three designs. Contrasting the non-dominated solution sets for each axis, it was found that only one design was common to both the pitch and roll axis. Thus, making that design the optimal combination of design parameter settings.

When the optimal parameter levels were used in the dynamic model, the results indicated a significant improvement in both the mean response and the signal to noise ratio of the stability performance variable. As expected, the optimal pitch design out performed all other designs in both mean response and signal to noise ratio in the pitch axis. Similarly, the optimal roll design out performs all other designs in both mean response and signal to noise ratio.

Evaluation of New Design

As a measure of the effectiveness of the design technique used to increase the stability of the vehicle, the resulting optimal vehicle stability characteristics were compared to those of the previous vehicle. The redesigned vehicle showed significant improvement in its ability to withstand the test scenario of a 20 mile per hour wind gust. The results indicate that the redesigned vehicle out performs the original design in its mean stability response and signal to noise ratio. Thus, the goal of improving the stability characteristics of a flight vehicle were achieved. Also, the desire of developing a system that was as robust as possible to the external factors beyond the designer control was accomplished.

Throughout the design process the goal of the analysis was to increase the dynamic stability of the flight vehicle. It was shown that the dynamic stability of the vehicle was improved as a result of this analysis. But, how does the improvement of the vehicles dynamic stability improve the combat capability of the weapon system? In order to show the improvement in combat capability the dynamic stability characteristics of the flight vehicle must be translated into operational requirements.

One of the selected missions for this particular vehicle was an attack/ assault mission where the flight vehicle utilizes an M136 84mm recoilless weapon. To be effective in its operational mission the vehicle must be stable enough to allow the weapon to hit its designated target. To quantify and compare the stability of the flight vehicle before parameter design and after parameter design the system transfer functions for the vehicles were calculated and used to form the dispersion regions for the two designs. The regions represent a 99% confidence limit on the area inside

of which the weapon will hit, given that the center of the region is the aim point at the maximum effective range of the weapon.

The dispersion region for the flight vehicle before parameter design and after parameter design are shown in Figure 4. The dimensions for the vehicle before parameter design are about 33 inches horizontally and about one inch vertically. The smaller ellipse is the dispersion region for the vehicle after parameter design. The difference is due to the change in the dynamic characteristics of the transfer function of the vehicle as a result of the subsystem placement. It is evident that the combat capability of the flight vehicle has been increased in that there is now a higher probability of hitting the intended target as shown by the dispersion regions.

Figure 1: Response Surface Roll Axis, Setting 1

Figure 2: Response Surface Roll Axis, Setting 2

Figure 3: Response Surface Roll Axis, Setting 3

Figure 4: Dispersion Regions

Conclusions

The results of this study show that there is benefit in using the quality techniques presented early in the design of future weapon systems. It was shown that there were many complex interactions that could not have been predicted had this structured analysis approach not been taken. The essential benefit of this approach is that it allows the designers to see the elements of a system that truly affect the operational performance of the system under study. As shown in this paper this complex set of interactions can be shown graphically as well as numerically. The techniques used in this study offer the designers advanced warning to potential weaknesses in the system design.

As the design process proceeds through each phase this set of quality tools can be applied and each time it is used new insight into system performance will be gained. This process also allows the designer to reduce over designed systems without causing problems in the operational effectiveness of the system. The largest disadvantage of this technique is that it costs money to perform these types of design analyses in the early stages of the design process. But, the payoff for this investment of dollars upfront will result in increased combat capability at decreased system cost. This technique of quality engineering as developed by Taguchi should become a required step in the systems engineering process that is used by today's defense contractors.

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